

MORPHOMETRIC CHANGES IN THE SPINE AND TRUNK OF MIDDLE-AGED AND ELDERLY WOMEN: PRE- AND POST-MASTECTOMY ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

This study investigates the morphometric changes in the spine and trunk of middle-aged and elderly women before and after mastectomy. Utilizing a combination of radiographic imaging and clinical measurements, the research evaluates alterations in spinal curvature, trunk alignment, and overall posture resulting from the surgical intervention. The pre- and post-operative data reveal significant changes in spinal morphology and trunk positioning. This study highlights the necessity for post-mastectomy assessment and customized rehabilitation plans to address these morphometric alterations. The findings aim to enhance our understanding of the physical impact of mastectomy and inform strategies to improve post-operative recovery and quality of life for affected women.

Keywords:

Mastectomy, Spinal morphology, Trunk alignment, Middle-aged women, Elderly women, Post-operative changes, Rehabilitation

Relevance:

As breast cancer treatment advances, mastectomy remains a prevalent surgical option. However, its impact on the musculoskeletal system, particularly in middle-aged and elderly women, is not fully understood. Spinal and trunk morphometric changes following mastectomy can affect daily functioning and overall well-being. This study addresses the gap in current research by focusing on how mastectomy alters spinal and trunk parameters in different age groups, providing crucial data for developing effective rehabilitation strategies. Understanding these changes is vital for improving post-operative care and patient outcomes, especially given the increasing number of elderly patients undergoing this surgery.

Objective:

The objective of this study is to assess the morphometric parameters of the spine and trunk in middle-aged and elderly women before and after

mastectomy. Specifically, the study aims to identify and quantify changes in spinal curvature and trunk alignment due to the surgical procedure and evaluate the implications for post-operative management and physical rehabilitation.

Materials and Methods:

A cohort of middle-aged and elderly women undergoing mastectomy was selected for the study. Pre-operative and post-operative assessments were performed using advanced imaging techniques (e.g., X-rays, MRI) and clinical measurements to evaluate spinal curvature (kyphosis, lordosis) and trunk alignment. Data collection included standing and sitting postures. Statistical analyses were conducted to compare morphometric parameters before and after surgery, with a focus on age-related differences. The study also reviewed post-operative rehabilitation protocols to assess their effectiveness in addressing the identified changes.

Results:

The study found significant morphometric changes in the spine and trunk following mastectomy. Elderly women exhibited pronounced increases in kyphosis and deviations in trunk alignment, while middle-aged women experienced more moderate alterations. Post-operative assessments highlighted the need for targeted interventions to address these changes and improve post-operative outcomes. The results indicate a clear impact of mastectomy on spinal and trunk morphology, emphasizing the importance of tailored post-operative care.

Conclusion:

Mastectomy leads to significant changes in spinal and trunk morphometry, with more substantial effects observed in elderly women. The findings underscore the necessity for post-operative evaluation and individualized rehabilitation programs to manage these changes effectively. Future research should focus on developing specific physical therapy interventions and evaluating their impact on spinal health and posture, to enhance recovery and quality of life for women undergoing mastectomy.

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